

Preparation and Properties of Highly Concentrated Sols. Part II. Sols of Vanadium Pentoxide, Silicic Acid and Molybdic Acid.

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In a recent communication (Mitra and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 315) the methods of preparation and properties of highly concentrated sols of ferric, chromic and aluminium hydroxides have been investigated. In this communication, we are presenting the results obtained with concentrated sols of vanadium pentoxide, silicic acid and molybdic acid.

In several publications from these laboratories, (compare Ghosh and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 1905) we have emphasised that, some properties of the sols of vanadium pentoxide, silicic, titanio, antimonio, tungstic and molybdic acids are fundamentally different from those of the sols of ferric, chromic, aluminium and other hydroxides, because the first group of sols is always associated with some amount of the acids in the dissolved condition. The behaviour of this group of hydroxide sols is far more complicated than that of the other hydroxide sols, e. g., $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, etc.

Vanadium Pentoxide Sol.

This sol was prepared according to the method of Biltz. A known weight of ammonium vanadate was made into a pasty mass in a pestle and mortar by adding small quantities of water and an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid was added to it, drop by drop. The red precipitate obtained was removed to a filter paper and washed till it had the tendency to pass into colloidal condition. The precipitate was removed in a Jena glass bottle and vigorously shaken with the addition of a small quantity of water till a clear deep red sol was obtained. The sol was further purified by dialysis. The experiments were carried in a thermostat at 30°

From day to day as the dialysis was in progress, the concentration, density, viscosity and the coagulation of the sol by electrolytes were

determined with increasing purity of the sol. The following are the experimental results :

TABLE I.

Sol A. Conc. = 14.72 g. V_2O_5
per litre.

Viscosity of water at 30° = 0.00803.

Days dialysed.	Conc. g./litre.	Density.	Viscosity.
0	14.72	1.010	0.02035
1	14.20	1.009	0.02103
2	13.48	1.011	0.02111
3	13.36	1.009	0.02127
6	13.13	1.009	0.23989
7	13.00	1.012	0.36294
8	12.44	1.013	Highly viscous

TABLE II.

Sol B. Conc. = 23.34 g. V_2O_5
per litre.

Days dialysed.	Conc. g./litre.	Density.	Viscosity.
1	23.34	1.005	0.02984
2	22.96	1.006	0.03068
3	21.60	1.006	0.03229
4	21.50	1.114	0.03281
5	21.42	1.114	0.04489
6	21.26	1.101	0.10355
7	20.56	1.101	0.16870
9	19.94	1.101	Highly viscous
10	19.40	1.101	Jelly formed

The influence of the concentration on the viscosity of vanadium pentoxide sol of different degrees of purity was investigated and the results are as follows :

TABLE III.

Sol dialysed for 1 day.		Sol dialysed for 6 days.	
Conc. g./litre.	Viscosity.	Conc. g./litre.	Viscosity.
14.2	0.02103	13.12	0.23989
7.1	0.01282	6.56	0.01218
5.55	0.01026	3.28	0.01002
2.84	0.00959	2.624	0.00945
1.42	0.00851	1.312	0.00879
0.71	0.00834	0.656	0.00854

The coagulation of the vanadium pentoxide sol by potassium and barium chlorides was determined at 30° and 60° in order to find out the influence of temperature on coagulation of the sol. The following are the experimental results ;

TABLE IV.

Sol A. Conc. = 14.72g. V_2O_5 per litre.

Total volume = 6 c.c. Time = 1 hour.

Days dialysed.	Temp. 30°			Temp. 60°		
	Amt. of N/20-KCl.	Amt. of N/50-BaCl ₂ .	Ratio of ppt. conc.	Amt. of N/20-KCl.	Amt. of N/50-BaCl ₂ .	Ratio of ppt. conc.
0	1.81 c.c.	0.82 c.c.	7.30	2.00 c.c.	0.61 c.c.	3.2
1	1.75	0.61	7.17	1.95	0.60	8.125
2	1.59	0.57	7.00	1.78	0.56	7.95
3	1.48	0.54	6.85	1.66	0.53	7.83
6	1.38	0.52	6.68	1.54	0.50	7.70
7	1.26	0.50	6.30	1.43	0.49	7.31
8	1.18	0.49	6.02	1.35	0.48	7.00

Sol B. Conc. = 23.34 g. V_2O_5 per litre.

1	1.97	0.60	8.21	2.60	0.70	9.29
2	1.82	0.57	8.00	2.40	0.67	8.95
3	1.66	0.54	3.68	2.28	0.65	8.60
4	1.44	0.50	7.20	1.97	0.60	8.21
5	1.25	0.46	6.80	1.72	0.54	7.96
6	1.14	0.44	6.48	1.53	0.50	7.65
7	1.06	0.42	6.31	1.40	0.47	7.45
9	1.01	0.41	6.16	1.33	0.45	7.39
10	0.96	0.40	6.00	1.20	0.44	6.82

The influence of the concentration of a sol on the amounts of electrolytes necessary for coagulation was also investigated with vanadium pentoxide sol and the results are as follows:

TABLE V.

Conc. = 14.72 g. V_2O_5 per litre.

Total volume = 6 c.c. Time = 1 hour. Temperature = 30°.

Days dialysed.	Dilution.	Amt. of N/20-KCl.	Amt. of N/50-BaCl ₂ .	Ratio.
9	original	1.01 c.c.	0.41 c.c.	6.16
10	"	0.96	0.40	6.00
9	10 times	1.60	0.12	31.26
10	"	1.40	0.12	29.17

TABLE VI.

Sol B. Conc. = 23.34 g. V_2O_5 per litre.
 Volume = 6 c.c. Time = 1 hour. Temp. = 30°.

Dilution.	Amt. of N/20-KCl to coagulate the fresh sol.	Amt. of N/20-KCl to coagulate the sol aged for 8 days.
B	1.12 c.c.	0.57 c.c.
B/6	1.37	0.47
B/10	1.49	0.42
B/20	1.56	0.38
B/40	1.58	0.36

Silicic Acid Sol.

A sol of silicic acid was prepared by the hydrolysis of silicon tetrachloride. A Kahlbaum sample of silicon tetrachloride was added drop by drop to ice cold water, and the sol thus formed was purified by dialysis.

The density, viscosity and coagulation of the sol were also investigated from day to day as the dialysis progressed. The results are as follows:

TABLE VII.

Days dialysed.	Sol A.			Sol B.		
	Conc.	Density at 30°.	Viscosity at 30°.	Conc.	Density at 30°.	Viscosity at 30°.
0	25.78	1.200	0.00965	32.32	1.223	0.00828
1	22.78	1.116	0.00983	30.48	1.182	0.00834
2	21.96	1.112	0.00994	29.12	1.143	0.00845
3	21.64	1.009	0.01047	29.00	1.110	0.00964
4	21.04	1.012	0.01256	28.23	1.098	0.00998
5	20.76	1.014	0.01269	27.62	1.100	0.01142
6	20.72	1.010	0.01312	27.02	1.09	0.01326
7	20.68	1.012	0.01503	26.34	1.07	0.02684
8	20.58	1.010	0.02084	25.89	1.06	0.1498
9	20.40	1.010	0.14460	25.34	1.06	0.2342
10	—	—	Highly viscous	—	—	Highly viscous

The influence of concentration on the viscosity of silicic acid sol of different degrees of purity was investigated and the results are as follows:

TABLE VIII.

Sol A.			
1st day of dialysis.		8th day of dialysis.	
Conc.	Viscosity.	Conc.	Viscosity.
24.62	0.01445	19.56	0.14980
12.31	0.01123	9.78	0.61504
6.15	0.00984	4.89	0.01266
4.92	0.00942	3.91	0.01082
2.46	0.00856	1.95	0.00981
1.23	0.00839	0.98	0.00877

Freshly prepared silicic acid sol cannot be coagulated by uni- and bivalent electrolytes but it becomes unstable in the presence of a small quantity of alkali. Hence the sol was always coagulated in the presence of small quantities of ammonium hydroxide and the results are as follows:

TABLE IX.

Conc. = 32.32 g. SiO_2 per litre. 0.2 C.c. of $N\text{-NH}_4\text{OH}$ added.

Time = 1 hour. Total volume = 6 c.c.

Days dialysed.	Temp. 30°			Temp. 60°		
	Amt. of 2N-KCl.	Amt. of N/10-BaCl ₂ .	Ratio.	Amt. of 2N-KCl.	Amt. of N/10-BaCl ₂ .	Ratio.
0	1.86 c.c.	0.80 c.c.	46.5	1.20 c.c.	0.66 c.c.	36.36
1	1.80	0.76	47.37	1.17	0.63	37.14
2	1.72	0.70	49.14	1.06	0.55	38.54
3	1.65	0.65	50.80	1.02	0.52	39.23
4	1.58	0.60	52.66	0.98	0.46	42.60
5	1.50	0.55	54.54	0.96	0.43	44.65
6	1.48	0.52	56.92	0.90	0.39	46.15
7	1.44	0.50	57.60	0.86	0.36	47.77
8	1.41	0.47	60.00	0.84	0.33	50.90
9	1.40	0.45	62.20	0.83	0.32	51.87

In order to study the influence on silicic acid sol, coagulation experiments were carried on with the sol sensitised by different amounts of ammonium hydroxide and the results are recorded below :

TABLE X.

Total volume = 6 c.c. Time = 1 hour. Temp. = 30°.

Sol dialysed for 2 days.		Conc = 7.52 g. SiO ₂ per litre.	
Amt. of 1.3 N-NH ₄ OH added.	Amt. of 3N-KCl necessary for coagulation.	Amt. of N/10-BaCl ₂ necessary for coagulation.	Ratio of ppt. conc., mono/bi.
0.20 c.c.	0.96 c.c.	1.01 c.c.	28.5
0.25	0.95	0.51	55.9
0.30	0.94	0.41	68.8
0.40	0.92	0.31	89.0

TABLE XI.

Sol dialysed for 4 days. Conc. = 5.78 g. SiO₂ per litre.

Total volume = 6 c.c. Time. = 1 hour. Temp. = 30°.

Amt. of N-NH ₄ OH added.	Amt. of 3N-KCl necessary for coagulation.	Amt of N/10-BaCl ₂ necessary for coagulation.	Ratio of ppt. conc., mono/bi.
0.2 c.c.	0.90 c.c.	0.23 c.c.	117.4
0.26	0.88	0.21	125.7
0.30	0.86	0.20	129.0
0.40	0.85	0.19	134.2

Molybdic Acid Sol.

Molybdic acid sol was prepared by the action of nitric acid on a concentrated solution of ammonium molybdate. The amount of nitric acid added was such that the white precipitate formed just redissolved. The sol was purified by dialysis.

The viscosity of the sol was practically the same as that of water at the same temperature, although the sol was highly concentrated.

The sol was coagulated by potassium chloride and barium chloride and the results are as follows :

TABLE XII.

Conc. = 128.62 g. MoO₃ per litre.

Vol. of the sol = 2 c.c. Total vol. = 6 c.c. Time = 1 hour.

Days dialysed.	Temp. 30°			Temp. 60°		
	Conc. necessary to coagulate		Ratio.	Conc. necessary to coagulate		Ratio.
	KCl.	BaCl ₂ .		KCl.	BaCl ₂ .	
1	0.1 N	0.00583 N	18.74	0.08 N	0.0035 N	22.86
2	0.0129 N	0.00133 N	9.70	0.0065 N	0.00066 N	9.65
3	0.00133 N	0.000166 N	8.00	0.0033 N	0.0004 N	8.26
4	0.000766 N	0.000107 N	7.16	0.0025 N	0.00032 N	7.61
5	0.00055 N	0.000093 N	5.91	0.00216 N	0.00031 N	7.00
6	0.00033 N	0.000070 N	4.71	0.00183 N	0.000266 N	6.18
7	0.00023 N	0.000053 N	4.34	0.00133 N	0.000276 N	4.84
8	0.000166 N	0.000043 N	3.86	0.001033 N	0.000266 N	3.88

Discussion.

From the foregoing tables, it will be clear that the viscosity of vanadium pentoxide and silicic acid sols increases markedly with their purity. This behaviour appears to be more pronounced with silicic acid sol than with vanadium pentoxide sol. The viscosity of undialysed and freshly prepared sol B of silicic acid, which is quite concentrated, does not differ very much from that of water; but after dialysis lasting for a week, the viscosity is greatly increased.

In order to obtain strictly comparable results we must take into consideration the influence of ageing on the properties of these sols. It has been emphasised in several publications that colloids have no definite composition, but it changes with time. The viscosity of sols of silicic and vanadic acids increases on ageing as

will be evident from the following results (cf. Ghosh and Dhar, *loc. cit.*).

Vanadium pentoxide sol. Conc. = 1.098 g./litre.		Silicic acid sol. Conc. = 12.075 g./litre.	
Date.	Viscosity (compared with water.)	Date.	Viscosity at 30°
4 Dec. 1922	1.090	7 April 1927	0.00872
6 Dec. 1922	1.085	2 May 1927	0.00919
8 Dec. 1922	1.100	13 July 1927	0.01121
18 Dec. 1922	1.110		
28 Dec. 1922	1.132		

Recently Chakravarti (D.Sc. Thesis, Allahabad University) has obtained exactly similar results on ageing with more concentrated sols of vanadium pentoxide.

On comparing these results on the influence of ageing on viscosity of sols of vanadium pentoxide and silicic acid with those obtained regarding the influence of purity on the viscosity of these sols, it will be clear that the latter influence is much more prominent than the former one. Thus with vanadium pentoxide sol, the ageing effect in 14 days is only a three per cent. increase of viscosity, whilst on purifying the sol for a week or so by dialysis, the viscosity of sols A and B are enormously increased, although the concentrations of the sols are less than those of the freshly prepared undialysed ones. Similarly with silicic acid sol, the viscosity increases about six per cent. in 25 days due to ageing, whilst after ten days dialysis, both the sols A and B become highly viscous. Consequently, even when we take into account the increase of viscosity of these sols on ageing, it will be evident that the viscosity increases with the dialysis of the sols. As the sols become purer and purer on dialysis, the adsorbed electrolyte becomes less and the electric charge on the particles of the sol decreases. Along with the decrease of the charge, the viscosity of the sol markedly increases. Hence these results obtained with vanadium pentoxide and silicic acid sols are in agreement with the conclusion of Dhar that the greater the purity and less the charge on the sol, the greater is its viscosity.

Chakravarti, Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 330) have deduced that if $N_1, N_2, N_3, \dots, N_x$ be the precipitating concentrations of uni-, bi-, tri-, ..., x valent ions, then

$$N_1 : N_2 : N_3 : \dots : N_x = 1 : \frac{1}{2} \alpha : 1/3 \alpha : \dots : 1/x \alpha^{x-1} \quad \text{where } \alpha = e^{-\frac{qe}{Dr}} / \frac{KT}$$

that is α lies between 0 and 1 and is a proper fraction, q = charge on

the colloid, D =dielectric constant of the medium, r =distance of the double layer, T =absolute temperature and K =Boltzmann constant. It follows from the foregoing relation that when T or D increases or q decreases, a tends to become unity. In other words, as the charge on the colloid particles decreases, the precipitating concentration of uni-, bi-, and trivalent ions tend to be in the ratio $1:\frac{1}{2}:\frac{1}{3}$.

Moreover, it follows from the above relation that when the temperature is increased, there should be a tendency of the precipitating concentrations to arrange in the ratio $1:\frac{1}{2}:\frac{1}{3}$.

The experimental results obtained with vanadium pentoxide and molybdic acid sols show that the ratio of the precipitating concentrations with potassium chloride and barium chloride appreciably decreases with the purity of the sols and these results are in agreement with the theoretical deductions of Chakravarti, Ghosh and Dhar already referred to.

It has already been stated that sols of vanadium pentoxide, silicic acid, molybdic acid and tungstic acid are always associated with the respective substance in the dissolved condition. With time the dissolved molecules, existing in large amounts in freshly prepared sols, agglomerate and form colloid particles, but on increasing the temperature of freshly prepared sols of vanadic and molybdic acids, the amount of dissolved substance is increased as will be evident in the case of vanadic acid from the following results obtained by Ghosh and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) with vanadium pentoxide sol:

Concentration of sol=7.41 g. V_2O_5 per litre.

Sol.	Amounts of V_2O_5 dissolved in 10 c.c. of sol.
Unboiled sol on 10 Nov. 1927	0.0088 g.
Unboiled sol on 12 Dec. 1927	0.0083
Boiled sol	0.0072

Now the stability of the sols of vanadic and molybdic acids increases with the increase in the amount of the dissolved acids, which yield negative ions adsorbable by the sols, and these sols are negatively charged. It is evident from the results recorded in this paper that the amounts of univalent positive ions required to coagulate these sols are much greater than the amounts of bivalent positive ions and consequently slight change in the stability of the sols is likely to

affect the precipitating concentration of potassium chloride more than that of barium chloride. Thus the ratio of the precipitating concentrations of potassium and barium chlorides is greater when the coagulation is carried at 60° than at 30°, because of the increased stability of the sol at 60°. This behaviour is observed only with the freshly prepared sols of vanadium pentoxide. With the aged sol of vanadium pentoxide, the amount of potassium chloride required for coagulation is less at 60° than at 30° (*cf.* Dhar and Satya Prakash, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 954).

The results on the coagulation of silicic acid sol by potassium and barium chlorides at 30° and 60° show that at 60°, the sol becomes unstable for both the electrolytes and the ratio of the precipitating concentration of potassium chloride to that of barium chloride is much less at 60° than at 30°. Consequently, this sol shows a different behaviour regarding its stability at higher temperatures from that of vanadic and molybdic acid sols. In precipitating silicic acid sol by electrolytes we have observed that the sol was extremely stable towards electrolytes and in order to effect precipitation by potassium and barium chlorides, the sol was mixed with traces of ammonium hydroxide, which sensitises the sol. In a previous communication, Ghosh and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) showed that the sensitising influence of traces of alkali is due to the formation of soluble silicates and dissolution of some of the complex and aggregated molecules of silicic acid.

It is obvious that the dissolution and the formation of silicate by the addition of traces of ammonium hydroxide is more pronounced at higher temperatures than at lower ones, and consequently, the sensitising influence of ammonium hydroxide towards silicic acid is greater at 60° than at 30° and the sol is less stable at 60° than at 30°.

Moreover, it will be seen that in the coagulation of silicic acid sol, which has been rendered unstable towards electrolytes by the addition of small quantities of ammonium hydroxide, the amount of barium chloride required for coagulation decreases more rapidly than the quantities of potassium chloride necessary for coagulation as the purity of the sol increases. It has also been observed in Tables X and XI that the decrease in the amount of barium chloride necessary for coagulating silicic acid sol in presence of increasing amounts of ammonium hydroxide acting as a sensitiser, is more pronounced than the decrease of the amount of potassium chloride under identical conditions.

It appears, therefore, that the sensitising influence of ammonium hydroxide on silicic acid sol is more pronounced on its coagulation by bivalent electrolytes than by monovalent ones and the increased purity of the silicic acid sol affects more markedly its coagulation by barium chloride than by potassium chloride. Hence these two properties of silicic acid sol appear to be related and seem to be due to the existence of the sol particles of different degrees of agglomeration along with the dissolved silicic acid and the possibility of forming sparingly soluble barium silicate on the addition of barium chloride to silicic acid containing small amounts of ammonium hydroxide.

These sols become unstable towards their coagulation by electrolytes on ageing as is generally observed with other sols. This behaviour may be ascribed to the formation of bigger aggregates from the colloidal particles on ageing and the consequent decrease in the number of the adsorbed stabilising ions. Moreover, these sols also become unstable on being heated specially when the sols are aged. We are of opinion that heating accentuates the ageing phenomenon specially with silicic acid sols and the stabilising ions are given out and thus the sols become unstable towards their coagulation, silicic acid sol being very sensitive to heat specially when aged. Thus a sol of silicic acid containing 22.54 g. of SiO_2 per litre sets to a stiff jelly on heating. Similar heat sensitivity of silicic acid sols has been reported by Flemming (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1902, **41**, 427) and Pauli and Valko (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, **38**, 289). In this respect silicic acid behaves like some typical lyophillic colloids. In previous papers (Dhar and Gore, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 31, 641) it has been reported that when the sols of ferric, chromic, aluminium and other hydroxides become highly pure they behave like lyophilic colloids regarding their viscosity. From the results recorded in Tables III and VIII, it appears that with pure sols of vanadium pentoxide and silicic acid, the viscosity-concentration relation is allied to that of a typical lyophillic colloid. The viscosity increases enormously in the concentrated condition and the viscosity-concentration curves are very steep.

The experimental results in Tables V and VI show that when vanadium pentoxide sol is freshly prepared, it requires greater amounts of potassium chloride for coagulation in the diluted condition than in the concentrated one. On the other hand, the aged sol requires smaller quantities of electrolytes for coagulation when diluted than the concentrated sol. The sols of vanadium pentoxide, silicic acid, molybdic acid, etc. always contain the respective acids in the dissolved

condition and the amount of acid present in the dissolved condition decreases with time due to their agglomeration to form sol particles. The negative ions given out by the acids are adsorbed by the sols and thus their electric charge is mainly due to this ionic adsorption. The antagonistic action of this stabilising ion is more pronounced in the coagulation of the diluted sol by an univalent ion than in the case of the concentrated sol, partly because of the greater ionisation of the dissolved acid when the sol is diluted. Hence larger quantities of potassium chloride are necessary for coagulating a freshly prepared and diluted sol than the concentrated one. When the sol becomes aged, the amount of dissolved acid existing along with the sol decreases and the influence of the stabilising ion becomes less marked and the sol requires smaller quantities of potassium chloride for coagulation when diluted than that required for coagulating the original sol. It appears that the behaviour of these sols is much more complicated than that of sols of ferric, chromic, and aluminium hydroxides. Further work with these sols, which are associated with the respective substances in the dissolved condition, is in progress.

Summary.

1. The viscosity of sols of vanadium pentoxide and silicic acid increases considerably with their purity. With the pure sols, the viscosity-concentration curves are very steep and resemble those of some lyophilic colloids. The viscosity of even a concentrated sol of molybdic acid is practically the same as that of water.

2. The ratio of the coagulating concentrations of potassium and barium chlorides decreases with the purity of sols of vanadium pentoxide and molybdic acid. Silicic acid sol can be coagulated by potassium and barium chlorides only when sensitised by ammonium hydroxide or any other alkali. In this case the ratio of the precipitating concentrations of potassium and barium chlorides increases with the purity of the sol.

3. The sensitising influence of ammonium hydroxide on silicic acid sol is more pronounced on its coagulation by bivalent ions than by monovalent ones. Moreover the increased purity of silicic acid sol affects more markedly its coagulation by bivalent ions than monovalent ions. These two properties appear to be related and are quite peculiar to silicic acid sol.

4. With silicic acid sol the ratio of the coagulating concentrations of potassium and barium chlorides is smaller at 60° than at 30°, whilst with vanadium pentoxide and molybdic acid the same ratio is greater at 60° than at 30°, specially when the sols are freshly prepared.

5. The properties of these sols are certainly more complicated than those of the other hydroxide sols, because these sols always contain the respective acids in the dissolved condition and these molecules have a tendency to agglomerate into sol particles.

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